

Cotton Plant Disease Prediction Using Deep Learning

Swathy Krishna
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
kanjirappally
Kottayam ,Kerala
swathykrishna2022b@mca.ajce.in

Ms.Jetty Benjamin
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering
Kanjirappally
Kottayam, Kerala
jettybenjamin@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— The use of deep learning models to identify lesions on cotton leaves based on images of the crop in the field is proposed in this work. It has become a target for a wide range of agricultural pests and diseases as a result of its tropical cultivation, demanding treatment. Furthermore, early indicators of significant pests and infections might be difficult to spot, making precise lesion diagnosis challenging for growers. The current research proposes a deep learning-based solution for cotton leaf screening to aid in the problem's resolution, allowing for better monitoring of the cotton crop's health and management decisions. The automated classifier CNN will be utilized in this technique to classify those two categories based on learning with certain training samples. Finally, simulation findings demonstrate that using a network classifier reduces training errors while improving classification accuracy.

Keywords—Plant disease, deep learning, CNN, Classification.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cotton is one of the most commercially significant crops used in the textile industry. It is grown in more than a hundred countries throughout the world, and in *Gossypium*spp. It was unsuccessful. because around 2.5 percent of the world's arable land is under cultivation. Cotton is referred to as "white gold". "The King of Fibers"

Agriculture is the backbone of Ethiopia's economy, providing 85 percent of employment and 90 percent of total international trade. Ethiopia is said to be good for a variety of agricultural products, including cotton. Traditional equipment and methods are unsuccessful. Using image processing techniques in an agricultural vision system, this study demonstrates how to diagnose cotton plant disease. Automatic plant disease detection is critical because it allows farmers to monitor large fields of crops and detect disease signs as soon as they appear on plant leaves. A farmer may find it difficult to recognize a variety of plant illnesses. Plant disease is predicted to cost the global economy \$60 billion in crop losses per year. because they take a lot of physical labour and time. A plant disease is a physiological abnormality and it is doomed if it becomes infected with a disease. It will show certain signs and symptoms. One of the signs is a change in the appearance of the eyes. Some of the symptoms include wilted leaf patches, rots, cankers, and other issues. The main goal of this model

is to identify and cure the disease in cotton plants. The CNN model is used to forecast whether or not the plant is sick

based on its position on the leaves. The proposed study employs the ensemble learning concept, which is implemented using a deep learning algorithm. The data is compared after deployment to discover which model is the most accurate.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Gokulnath BV and Usha Devi G, [1] The goal of this study was to conduct a survey on the use of machine learning and deep learning techniques to forecast plant disease. This aspect has an impact on plant production when it comes to predicting illness in plants. The machine learning method aids in the detection of plant disease. Random forest, Bayesian network, Decision Tree, Support Vector Machine, and other techniques are used. Plant disease is caused by a variety of circumstances. Plant pathology is primarily concerned with pathogen research. Pathogens and environmental conditions are the two elements that cause plant disease. Viruses, fungus, bacteria, and other microorganisms are examples.

Azath M., Melese Zekiwo, and Abey Bruck [2] Deep learning-based image processing was used in this work to diagnose cotton leaf disease and pests. Cotton, also known as *gossypiumsapp*, is also referred to as "white gold" and "the king of fibres." The goal of this research was to create a model for identifying cotton plants.

Kalpesh Shinde, Nishant Dhamale, Sudarshan Dangat, and Prof. Anand Khatri, [3] The detection of cotton lesions was reported in this work utilizing a deep learning approach. Here, deep learning technology is used to detect the cotton plant's leaf base in photos. Each picture is processed and evaluated separately. Here is the diagnosis algorithm: The lesson's casual agent suggested an algorithm for implementing software usage.

S.Nandhini and K. Ashokkumar [4] Crop disease prediction by machine learning from crop leaf images is the goal of this work. Plant diseases pose a significant threat to food security. The plant's illness is detected using a smartphone.

T.Linda J. Thomson , Sarina Macfadyen , and Ary A. Hoffmann [5] discuss the effect of climate change on natural enemies of natural pests. Climate change has an impact on plant productivity. Climate change will have an impact on the interactions between plants, natural enemies, and herbivores, demonstrating the difficulty of making predictions.

Rafael Faria Caldeira, Wesley Esdras Santiago and Barbara Teruel, [6] This paper uses deep learning techniques to identify the cotton leaf based on images of the crop. The images are pressed and analyzed individually. Here is the algorithm to diagnose the casual agent of the lesson. proposed algorithm for software implementation.

Chitranjan Kumar Rai, [7] The concept of deep learning was used to identify and predate the cotton plant disease using real-time images of leaves and plants. The DCNN architecture was used to automatically diagnose diseases in cotton leaves and plants by changing the parameters of the AlexNet architecture. On a test dataset of about 200 pictures, the recommended model functioned admirably. The rate of accuracy is 98 %. This research also shows how simple it is to implement this method. in order to obtain the required results.

Pratiti Saha and Dr. Nachappa MN, [8] Cotton plant disease prediction is widely used in agriculture. It's a sort of image processing used in vision systems that are automated. To assess whether or not the plant is infected, the CNN model is utilized. Several data mining models, for example, are used to successfully analyze data. Deep learning appears to have a lot of promise for organizations looking to enhance accuracy.

III. MOTIVATION

Human civilization has been able to generate enough food to feed approximately 7 billion people. Climate change, pollinator decline, and plant disease are the various issues that affect food security. In addition to that, crop plant disease is a worldwide problem, not just in one nation. They may be beneficial to food security, but they also have the potential to be devastating. Healthy crops are essential to people's livelihoods. Smallholder farms are home to the majority of hungry people (50%). As a result of the decrease in agricultural households, the number of small-scale farmers has decreased. They are more at risk.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to obtain the CNN model used to predict whether a plant is infected or not based on leaf area. The proposed research work serves the concept of integrated learning, done with a deep learning algorithm. The model should be able to distinguish between disease and a fresh leaf. The dataset is divided into two sets of training and testing data. The model should be trained with additional data to obtain reading accuracy. The result from this model can be used to create plant classifications. Modules for diagnosing plant diseases image collection, pre-image processing, image classification, and separator selection.

Figure 1:

Cotton Plant Disease Prediction Methodology

The steps that require to be followed are:

- Image collection
 - Pre-image processing
 - Image classification
 - Separator selection
- a. **Image collection** : For cotton plant disease prediction, the user must utilize a dataset, and the properties of this dataset are used to train the model.
 - b. **Pre-image processing**: Pre-processing is used to improve picture data by suppressing undesired distortions or enhancing other relevant image properties for later processing. For continuous segmentation, data is processed and sent.
 - c. **Image classification**: The process of splitting an enhanced image into distinct pieces is known as picture segmentation or classification
 - d. **Separator selection**: We're using CNN at this point to identify and Order the plant leaf diseases (Convolutional Neural Network). CNNs are commonly used for picture categorization and recognition. Convolutional Neural Networks specialized for application in images. CNN is mainly used in image analysis tasks like image recognition and Object detection & Segmentation.

V. BUILD MODEL

The building of a model is a critical step in the cotton plant disease prediction process. The users apply the algorithms to build the model. [9].

The steps involved are:


```
# run the resnet model
result = resnet_model.fit(
    training_set,
    validation_data=test_set,
    epochs=20,
    steps_per_epoch=len(training_set),
    validation_steps=len(test_set)
)
```

In this I have kept the epochs as 5 so the accuracy will be a bit less but if you increase the number of epochs, accuracy will definitely increase.

VI. RESULT

Based on the dataset provided, the prediction of cotton plant disease using deep learning may be classified as "fresh leave" or "disease". During training, the network classifier in use provides the least amount of error and the best degree of classification accuracy. The dataset contains images of different leaves that are fresh and diseased.

VII. CONCLUSION

This research describes a strategy for predicting cotton plant disease. A CNN model simulation is used to determine whether or not a plant is infected based on a spot on the leaves. The user first processed the data, then implemented a solution. To extract certain dataset characteristics, we used transfer learning resnet50. Then Finally, the simulated outcome reveals that network classifier in use produces the least amount of error during training and the highest level of classification accuracy. The dataset may be expanded, and deep learning algorithms or tools can be used to forecast cotton plant disease. This work has a lot of potential use in the future. Artificial neural networks (ANN) and convolutional neural networks (CNN) are the two most commonly used neural network models. The proposed algorithm will be implemented using software that can be used during actual field visits to aid in the construction of maps depicting the degree of pest and disease infestation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Gokulnath BV and Usha Devi G, "A Survey on Plant Disease Prediction using Machine Learning and Deep Learning Techniques", *Inteligencia Artificial*, 22(63) (2017), 0-19 doi:10.4114/intartif.vol22iss63pp0-1.
- [2] Azath M, Melese Zekiwos, and Abey Bruck, "Deep Learning-Based Image Processing for Cotton Leaf Disease and Pest Diagnosis," *Hindawi Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, Volume 2021, Article ID 9981437, 10 pages.
- [3] Kalpesh Shinde, Nishant Dhamale, Sudarshan Dangat and Prof. Anand Khatri, "CROP PREDICTION AND PLANT LEAF DISEASE PREDICTION USING DEEP LEARNING," *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, Volume: 08 Issue: 12 | Dec 2021.
- [4] S. Nandhini and K. Ashokkumar, "Machine Learning Technique for Crop Disease Prediction Through Crop Leaf Image" *Appl. Math. Inf. Sci.* 16, No. 2, 149-158 (2022) *Applied Mathematics & Information Sciences An International Journal* <http://dx.doi.org/10.18576/amis/160202>
- [5] Linda J. Thomson, Sarina Macfadyen and Ary A. Hoffmann a, "Predicting the effects of climate change on natural enemies of agricultural pests" 1049-9644/\$ - see front matter Crown Copyright 2009 Published by Elsevier Inc. All rights reserved. doi:10.1016/j.biocontrol.2009.01.022.
- [6] Rafael Faria Caldeira, Wesley Esdras Santiago and Barbara Teruel, "Identification of Cotton Leaf Lesions Using Deep Learning Techniques," *Sensors* 2021, 21, 3169. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21093169>
- [7] Chitrnanjan Kumar Rai, "Automatic Classification of Real-Time Diseased Cotton Leaves and Plants Using a Deep Convolutional Neural Network," March 14th, 2022 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1440994/v1>.
- [8] Pratiti Saha and Dr. Nachappa MN, "Cotton Plant Disease Prediction Using Deep Learning," *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET)* ISSN: 2321-9653; IC Value: 45.98; SJ Impact Factor: 7.538, Volume 10 Issue III Mar 2022. (references)
- [9] <https://www.kaggle.com/code/sameer1502/cotton-plants-disease-prediction-using-resnet50/notebook> The model building is the main step in the Cotton Plant Disease Prediction.